

BUILDING LAND COVER MAP FOR LAND MANAGEMENT IN KRONG BONG DISTRICT, DAK LAK PROVINCE

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SUMMARY

Over time, land cover has persistantly changed, especially under the strong impact of natural disasters, people with socio-economic development activities. Therefore studying the current state of the land cover is necessary. By integrating remote sensing and GIS, a land cover map with 6 classes was built for Krong Bong district in 2021 with overall accuracy of 75% and Kappa coefficient of 0.7. After the integration process in Krong Bong district, research indicated the main advantages and limitations, and then, some solutions have been proposed to promote the application of digital technology to improve the efficiency of land management in this area.

Keywords: *Sentinel-2A, GIS, Land cover, Krong Bong district, Land management.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Land cover is the physical cover observed by viewing from the ground or remote sensing satellites (FAO, 1998). Over time, land cover has persistantly changed, especially under the strong impact of natural disasters and people with socio-economic development activities. Therefore, studying the current state of the land cover is necessary to have solutions that limit the negative impacts of humans and respond to climate changes in the current context.

In recent years, the strong development of remote sensing satellites has affirmed the advantages of monitoring resources and the environment and made significant contributions to socio-economic development worldwide. Geographic information systems (GIS) and remote sensing (RS) techniques have continuously improved with increasingly sophisticated equipment systems and data quality. Therefore, the research, application and integration of RS and GIS data has been made in many fields. For example, applying RS and GIS to predict landslides (Nguyen Huu Ha et al., 2012; Vu Minh Tuan and Vu Xuan Cuong, 2013), drought monitoring (Duong Van Kham et al., 2013; Tran Thuc et al., 2013). For the land cover field, much research, such as building a map of mangrove forest status using Landsat 8 OLI images (Lam Van Tan et al., 2014); establishing land cover maps (Nguyen Thi Ngoc Quyen et al., 2016; Ho Le Thu, 2020); assessing the land use change (Dang Ngoc Quoc Hung and Ho Dac Thai Hoang, 2016). Thus, the integration of remote sensing and

GIS is an inevitable trend in resource management. Clearly, building land cover/land use change map using RS and GIS takes a shorter time and lower price than previous mapping technology.

Krong Bong is located in a remote district of Dak Lak province (Fig.1). It is far from 50km south of Buon Ma Thuot city. It has 125,695.23 hectares of natural area, but 90.74% is agricultural land (Dak Lak Department of Natural Resources and Environment, 2021). The fact is that the application of scientific and technical achievements in resource management and monitoring in the district is minimal. Therefore, the study aims to build the land cover map of Krong Bong district, Dak Lak province by integrating GIS and RS to assess the land potential to serve land management in the research area.

Fig.1. Krong Bong administrative boundary map

2. CONTENTS AND METHODS

2.1. Contents

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- Land cover classification using Sentinel-2A satellite image;
- Building Krong Bong land cover map;
- Identifying the advantages and disadvantages of integrating GIS and RS to build the land cover map at the research area;
- Proposing some solutions to improve the efficiency of land management.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Secondary data collection method

Secondary data were collected from authorities such as the Departments of Natural Resources and Environment of Dak Lak province and Krong Bong district. The data include natural conditions in the study area; land use and management situation; thematic maps; and documents related to the research contents

2.2.2. Field survey method

This method is carried out in the field to double-check the information and facts collected during the internal investigation and supplement the missing information to complete the information and data.

In this study, we surveyed the current land use/land cover and the distribution rules of ones in the study area. Besides, we compared the classification areas on the image and in the field to verify the interpretation results to check again the classification accuracy.

2.2.3. Primary data collection method

Sample points for image classification were collected by GPS. In the field, each different state was taken coordinates and described the form of the overlay. For an overlay, the minimum number of field points required is equal to the number of spectral bands plus 1 (Nguyen Thi Thanh Huong, 2015). Thus, with 6 layers of land cover classified as non-expertise and 12 spectral bands of Sentinel-2A satellite images, 78 field sites are required in the Krong Bong district. However, in order to increase the accuracy of the classification process, the study identified 120 field sites to conduct the classification and randomly selected 60 points to test the results after the classification.

2.2.4. Integrating GIS and remote sensing data methods

Sentinel-2A images are classified according to the following process:

- The collected satellite image data has no registered coordinates, so it is necessary to assign

the image to the same map coordinate system.

- Enhancing image quality to clarify objects of interest and compositing images for classification.

• Image classification: Supervised method is often used in land cover classification. This method can arrange user-defined pixels into different classes, where all pixels on an image are identified through similar spectral notation to realize identity. Training samples have other performance characteristics that the researcher wants to classify. The selection of appropriate training samples is based on observations and is supported by various types of maps and field survey data.

• Post-classification accuracy: The result of a match between the types of land cover and those predicted by a classification algorithm usually performed by an error matrix. To establish the error matrix, the analyst must compare the classification results over the available area on a pixel-by-pixel basis and determine the degree of accuracy at the verified locations through the accuracy criteria: overall accuracy, producer accuracy and user accuracy (Le Van Trung, 2015).

- Overall accuracy:

$$T = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^K O_j}{n} \times 100$$

- Producer accuracy:

$$t_{i+1} = \frac{S_{i+} - O_j}{S_{i+}} \times 100$$

- Use accuracy:

$$t_{+j} = \frac{S_{+j} - O_j}{S_{+j}} \times 100$$

Where: O_{ji} is the value representing the match in row i and column j ; S_{i+} is the total value in row ($i=1,2,\dots,k$); S_{+j} is the total value in column ($j=1,2,\dots,k$); n is the total number of pixels in the dataset.

- Kappa (k) coefficient:

$$K = \frac{P \sum_i x_{ii} - \sum_i x_i + x+i}{P^2 - \sum_i x_i + x+i}$$

Where: P is the total number of pixels in all right classes on the ground; x_{ii} is the sum of correctly classified pixels lying on the diagonal of the error matrix; x_i is the total number of correct pixels on the ground in a class; $(x+i)$ is the total number of pixels classified in that class.

Table 1. Value of Kappa coefficient in the accuracing of the image classification results

K index	Levels
< 0.00	Weak
0.00 – 0.20	Light
0.21 – 0.40	Medium
0.41 – 0.60	Quite good
0.61 – 0.80	Good
0.81 – 1.00	Very good

Source: Navulur, 2007

• Building land cover map: if the classification results's accuracy is significant (accuracy criteria get equal or over 50% and the Kappa coefficient gets equal or over 0.5), the smoothed image will be eligible to build land cover map.

GIS and RS integration steps in image processing and land cover map building are done in the working environment of ArcGIS 10.8 software.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Sentinel-2A image classification

3.1.1. Image processing

Sentinel-2A image was downloaded at website: <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>. The image had to take in Krong Bong district with suitable time and cloud cover under 10% (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Choose Sentinel-2A image

After downloading, the image was processed by ArcGIS software. However, the image bands added to ArcGIS were a single band with monochromatic colors. The fact is that the eyes or computers cannot classify it. Therefore, the Sentinel-2A image was composited from 3 bands 11, 8A and 4, with a resolution of 10 meters. These three bands, which were combined, were created as suitable pseudo-colors to detect land cover. Then, the image was clipped according to the boundary of the study area (Fig. 3).

Fig 3. Clipped image according to the boundary of Krong Bong district

3.1.2. Image classification

Drawing classified sample

A file containing the field points that GPS has taken needs import into Excel software to draw the classification sample. Next, they were represented spatially and displayed the labels of those points in ArcGIS software (Fig 4).

Fig 4. Drawing classified sample at Sentinel-2A

As can be seen, a land cover was drawn with many sample areas. They were the individual ROIs for each land cover layer, and they needed to merge these single ROIs into a unified ROI. Then, they were saved and analysed pixel values (curve spectral values) in the sample area by Create Signatures tool or create a spectral curve right on the Training Sample Manager panel (Fig 5).

ID	Class Name	Value	Color	Count
1	WATER	1		496
2	FOREST	6		94622
3	SPECIAL	11		743
4	PADDY	16		753
5	PERENNIAL	21		431
6	ANNUAL	26		370

Fig 5. Standardized classified data

Principal Components Analysis

A satellite image contains typical multi-bands data with a high correlation (the correlation between two bands represents the level of

similar information given by these two bands). Bands with high correlation are not usually used simultaneously for color rendering or extracting similar spectral reflectance objects.

Fig 6. PCA in Sentinel-2A image

The next step in image processing is principal component analysis (PCA). This is a technique that converts the grayscale values of pixels, and this transformation compresses the image data by keeping the maximum amount of useful information and eliminating duplicate information (correlation factors). As a result, the new image (called principal component image) contains only less correlated image bands that are often used very effectively in image composition and classification (Fig 6).

Image classification

Image classification is assigning suitable classes with features to group similar features to separate distinct features from each other in the image. In Krong Bong district, the classification is carried out based on composite images from three bands 11, 8A and 4. These are three bands of pseudo-color combination that are classified the land cover of Sentinel-2A images. The steps are performed in the working environment of ArcGIS with the Classification and Maximum Likelihood Classification tool.

Fig 7. Image classification

As a result, we have a new images that has been classified according in 6 layers of land cover, including (1) paddy land, (2) perennial cropland, (3) annual cropland, (4) forest land (deciduous forest, evergreen forest, mixed forest), (5) special-use land (residential land, building land, traffic land), (6) water surface (Fig 7).

Nevertheless, the classification results of land cover

layers are still fragmented. Therefore, in the next step, we proceed to smooth them with the Majority Filter function in Generalization of the ArcToolBox.

Fig 8. Smooth the classification result

3.1.3. Accuracy the classification results

Accuracy evaluation is an algorithm that determines the reliability of the image classification. The method for evaluating classification accuracy is based on a square matrix arranged in rows and columns specifying the number of pixel samples assigned to a particular class relative to the current classes. This study's accuracy step was conducted in ArcGIS software with the process below.

Firstly, validation points were established by random method with the support of Spatial Analysis Tools/ Segmentation and Classification/ Create Accuracy Assessment Points. Specifically, 60 random points were created to calculate the classification accuracy of the Krong Bong district image.

Next, we compared these random points with the field by Arctoolbox, selected Extraction/ Extract value to point to create DKD_Value file. Finally, the composite image was displayed to observe the newly created validation points and confirmed whether they were right or wrong. After testing 60 points, we determine the accuracy evaluation criteria through a matrix table in the working environment of ArcGIS using the Compute Confusion Matric Tool.

OBJECTID*	ClassValue	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	C_5	C_6	Total	U_Accuracy	Kappa
1	C_1	9	1	0	0	0	0	10	0.9	0
2	C_2	0	10	0	0	0	0	10	1	0
3	C_3	0	0	6	0	3	1	10	0.6	0
4	C_4	0	0	0	9	1	0	10	0.9	0
5	C_5	0	1	0	0	7	2	10	0.7	0
6	C_6	2	3	0	1	0	4	10	0.4	0
7	Total	11	15	6	10	11	7	60	0	0
8	P_Accuracy	0.818182	0.666667	1	0.9	0.636364	0.571429	0	0.75	0
9	Kappa	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.7

Fig 9. Accuracy the classification results in ArcGIS

According to the accuracy of classifying six land cover layers, the overall accuracy reached 75%; Kappa coefficient is 0.7, which showed a good result in Table 1 at the methods part. Moreover, the classification accuracy is also calculated with producer accuracy and user accuracy, as depicted

in Figure 9. In sum, the classification results of land cover guarantee reliability in establish a land cover map in Krong Bong district.

3.2. Building land cover map in Krong Bong

In the working environment of ArcGIS, the results of the classification of Sentinel-2A satellite images were edited to create a land cover map in Krong Bong district with 1:250,000 scale. (Fig 10).

After that, the land cover area was extracted from the map to demonstrate its structure and support in the land management of Krong Bong district. According to Table 2, this district has a total natural area of 125,695.23 hectares, divided into 6 land cover layers. The largest layer was forestry land, which accounted for 60,319.22 hectares and 48.35% of the total natural area. Perennial crops came in second with 39,307.15 hectares and 31.27% of the total natural area. Finally, specialized land accounted for 12.98% of the total natural area and the remaining land cover comprised less than 5% of the total.

Fig 10. Land cover map at Krong Bong district

Table 2. The land cover area in Krong Bong district in 2021

Land cover	Area (hectares)	Ratio (%)
Water surface	313.85	0.25
Forestry land	60,774.79	48.35
Special-use land	16,319.22	12.98
Paddy land	2,908.62	2.31
Perennial cropland	39,307.15	31.27
Annual cropland	6,071.60	4.83
Total	125,695.23	100.00

3.3. Advantages and disadvantages in integrating GIS and RS to build the land cover map in Krong Bong district

3.3.1. Advantages

Satellite images are now increasingly high resolution and better preprocessed than in the past.

Not out of the trend, GIS software in general and ArcGIS, in particular, are increasingly developed, perfected, and integrated with more functions in processing and classifying satellite images; data analysis: distance, overlay, network; display data in the form of charts, maps, reports; Export data: paper maps, internet, image files, documents.

The inputs in GIS are vector and raster forms, and remote sensing data is likewise in raster format; as a result, combining remote sensing and GIS makes it simple to develop numerous valuable applications to support the management of land resources in Krong Bong district, particularly in term of updating speed based on a rapid iteration cycle of satellite images. Moreover, remote sensing and GIS data have the exact reference coordinates, so the similarity in processing techniques between remote sensing image and GIS creates an argument in favour of integrating of them.

Last but not least, the function of overlaying data layers allows the integration and display of both vector and raster layers simultaneously. This quickly update data layers on traffic, hydrogeology and land cover into background data and thematic data layers of GIS. They will support land use changes and land management assessments in the Krong Bong district.

3.3.2. Disadvantages

Free image has medium resolution, so the classification results are not detailed enough to determine the types of land classified according to the use purpose, which was regulated by Land Law 2013.

The total natural area of Krong Bong district extracted from the land cover map was not equal to the whole natural area according to land statistics and inventory of the authorities. Specifically, the total natural location on the land cover map was more extensive than land statistics results in 2021 about 347.07 hectares. This was explained by the algorithms that generate the natural phenomena into the model, always having specific errors. Therefore, internal steps are needed to eliminate these errors to make them suitable for legal data.

Comparing the land statistics at Krong Bong district with the land covers on the map, there was no significant difference in forestry land and paddy land because they are easily detected on the satellite image with the eyes, and the sample drawing process got a relatively constant value. However, other land covers vary considerably due to the misclassification of annuals with perennials or vegetation over water areas. Thereby, it can be denied that the Sentinel-2A satellite image with 10

metters x 10 metters resolution was suitable for application in forestry land management or cover types with uniformity and concentrated planting area such as paddy. On the other hand, remaining land covers need to use higher resolution remote sensing images combined with detailed fieldwork.

3.4. Solutions to improve the efficiency of land management in Krong Bong district

The biggest limitation in land management in Krong Bong district is that technology has not been applied to managing and assessing land use change because human resources have not been trained, fostered, or approached with new scientific advances. Besides, the population is still sparse, socio-economic conditions are not developed, and most of the natural land area is forest, so the traditional method of land management is still the primary method. Therefore, some solutions are proposed based on the advantages of integrating GIS and remote sensing below.

Implement the application of modern information technology, especially specialized software, to land management, ease administrative procedures, modernize construction and establish a thematic map.

The hilly terrain makes it very difficult to make a land cover map in the Krong Bong district. Therefore, intergarting GIS and RS is an excellent solution to making the land cover map. Then, based on the current land use maps established from the satellite image, building land planning will suit the future development conditions in the study area.

Regular professional training for commune-level cadastral staff, especially on information technology application and investment in

equipment for long-term use of land management.

The application of GIS and RS in the inspection of land management and use in the locality to promptly correct errors, promote positive factors, and contribute to the land management in the locality will be completed and effective in the coming time.

4. CONCLUSION

Sentinal-2A satellite image was used to create the land cover map in Krong Bong district by supervised classification method with the Maximum Likelihood algorithm. As a result, 6 different land covers were identified with a kappa coefficient of 0.7 and overall accuracy of 75%; the total natural area classified from the Sentinel-2A image was 126,042.3 hectares, of which: (1) water surface 313.85 hectares, (2) Forest land with 60,774.79 hectares, (3) Specialized land with 16,666.29 hectares; (4) Paddy land 2,908.62 hectares, (5) perennial cropland with 39,307.15 hectares, (6) annual cropland with 6,071.6 hectares.

The advantage of integrating GIS and RS is that satellite images are getting higher and higher resolution, and GIS tools are becoming more and more perfect and developed with tools to support the processing and analysis, classification, accuracy assessment, and map editing in just one unified environment. Meanwhile, the biggest limitation is the average resolution satellite image, which is unsuitable for land management that requires high accuracy.

The solution to promoting the application of technology in land management is regular professional training for commune officials. The first is to encourage and then mandate the application of digital technology in local land management.

XÂY DỰNG BẢN ĐỒ LỚP PHỦ ĐẤT KHÔNG NGỪNG BIẾN ĐỔI, NHẤT LÀ DƯỚI TÁC ĐỘNG MẠNH CỦA THIÊN TAI, CỌN NGƯỜI VỚI CÁC HOẠT ĐỘNG PHÁT TRIỂN KINH TẾ - XÃ HỘI NÊN VIỆC NGHIÊN CỨU HIỆN TRẠNG LỚP PHỦ ĐẤT LÀ CẦN THIẾT. BẰNG CÁCH TÍCH HỢP VIỄN THĂM VÀ GIS, BẢN ĐỒ LỚP PHỦ ĐẤT VỚI 6 LOẠI SỬ DỤNG ĐẤT ĐÃ ĐƯỢC XÂY DỰNG CHO HUYỆN KRÔNG BÔNG VÀO NĂM 2021 VỚI ĐỘ CHÍNH XÁC TỔNG THỂ LÀ 75% VÀ HỆ SỐ KAPPA LÀ 0,7. SAU QUÁ TRÌNH TÍCH HỢP TẠI HUYỆN KRÔNG BÔNG, NGHIÊN CỨU ĐÃ CHỈ RA NHỮNG THUẬN LỢI VÀ HẠN CHẾ CHÍNH, TỪ ĐÓ ĐƯA RA MỘT SỐ GIẢI PHÁP ĐỀ ĐÃY MẠNH ỨNG DỤNG CÔNG NGHỆ SỐ NHẪM NÂNG CAO HIỆU QUẢ QUẢN LÝ ĐẤT ĐAI TẠI KHU VỰC NÀY.

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TÓM TẮT

Theo thời gian, lớp phủ đất không ngừng biến đổi, nhất là dưới tác động mạnh của thiên tai, cọn người với các hoạt động phát triển kinh tế - xã hội nên việc nghiên cứu hiện trạng lớp phủ là cần thiết. Bằng cách tích hợp viễn thám và GIS, bản đồ lớp phủ đất với 6 loại sử dụng đất đã được xây dựng cho huyện Krông Bông vào năm 2021 với độ chính xác tổng thể là 75% và hệ số Kappa là 0,7. Sau quá trình tích hợp tại huyện Krông Bông, nghiên cứu đã chỉ ra những thuận lợi và hạn chế chính, từ đó đưa ra một số giải pháp đề đẩy mạnh ứng dụng công nghệ số nhằm nâng cao hiệu quả quản lý đất đai tại khu vực này.

Từ khoá: Sentinel-2A, GIS, Thảm phủ, Huyện Krông Bông, Quản lý đất đai.

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